

ANALISIS KEBUTUHAN BAHAN AJAR KIMIA ORGANIK YANG BERORIENTASI *HIGHER ORDER THINKING SKILLS*

Helda Rahmawati¹, Ratna Kartika Irawati²

^{1,2}Tadris Kimia, Universitas Islam Negeri Antasari
Jalan A. Yani Km 4,5, Kebun Bunga, Banjarmasin, Kalimantan Selatan, Indonesia
¹e-mail: helda.rahmawati@uin-antasari.ac.id

Submitted
2023-02-04

Accepted
2023-03-20

Published
2023-06-11

Abstrak

Tujuan penelitian untuk menganalisis kebutuhan bahan ajar Kimia Organik yang berorientasi *higher order thinking skills*. Penelitian yang dilakukan termasuk penelitian kuantitatif deskriptif dengan populasi penelitian sebanyak 19 orang mahasiswa Tadris Kimia UIN Antasari angkatan 2018. Teknik sampel yang digunakan adalah sampel jenuh. Alat pengumpulan data menggunakan angket dan dokumentasi. Data dianalisis secara deskriptif. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa: mahasiswa sulit memahami materi Kimia Organik dengan tepat; mahasiswa sulit menemukan sumber belajar yang berhubungan dengan Kimia Organik; bahan ajar yang digunakan saat pembelajaran Kimia Organik kurang menarik dan tidak kontekstual; bahan ajar Kimia Organik yang digunakan tidak mendukung mahasiswa untuk menemukan konsep sendiri; serta bahan ajar yang digunakan tidak membantu meningkatkan *higher order thinking skills*. Berdasarkan hasil penelitian, disimpulkan bahwa semua responden menyatakan perlunya dikembangkan bahan ajar Kimia Organik yang membuat lebih aktif dan membantu meningkatkan keterampilan berpikir tingkat tinggi.

Kata Kunci: analisis kebutuhan; bahan ajar; *higher order thinking skills*.

Abstract

The research aimed to analyze the needs for Organic Chemistry teaching materials that are oriented to higher order thinking skills. The research method used descriptive quantitative research with a research population was 19 of Tadris Chemistry students at UIN Antasari class of 2018. The sampling technique used a saturated sample. Data collection tools used questionnaires and documentation. Data were analyzed descriptively. The results showed that: it was difficult for students to understand Organic Chemistry material correctly; it was difficult for students to find learning resources related to Organic Chemistry; teaching materials used when learning Organic Chemistry were less interesting and not contextual; Organic Chemistry teaching materials used do not support students to find their own concepts; and the teaching materials used do not help improve higher order thinking skills. Based on the research results, it was concluded that all respondents stated the need to develop Organic Chemistry teaching materials that make them more active and help improve higher order thinking skills.

Keywords: needs analysis; teaching materials; *higher order thinking skills*.